

Innovation and Competitiveness of Selected Small and Medium-scale Enterprises (SMES) in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Small and Medium-scale Enterprises (SMES) are firms that act as catalysts and have been seen to support a country's growth and development. Despite concerted efforts from different stakeholders to improve the output of SMES, they still do not meet the standards that are required of them. The population of this study consist of SMES management staff of the selected SMES in Lagos State. The population comprised 8,396 owners/managers of SMES. The sample size was 471 and a stratified random sampling technique was employed. An adapted and validated questionnaire was administered to the respondents and the data gathered was analysed using multiple linear regression analysis. Innovation variables were found to have a significant combined effect on the competitiveness of selected SMES in Lagos State, Nigeria ($R = 0.379$, $AdjR^2 = 0.136$, $p < 0.05$). Product innovation with ($\beta = 0.222$; $p = 0.033 < 0.05$), process innovation with ($\beta = 0.478$; $p = 0.023 < 0.05$) and market innovation with ($\beta = 1.028$; $p = 0.015 < 0.05$). The study concludes that innovation has a significant effect on the competitiveness of SMES in Lagos State Nigeria. The study recommends that more efforts on innovation should be by SMES to sustain competitiveness.

Keywords: Innovation, Competitiveness, SMES

Introduction

Small and medium-sized businesses (SMES) are renowned for serving as growth and development drivers for nations, consistently increasing a nation's gross domestic product (GDP) and enhancing per capita income and productivity. In addition to this, SMES are also responsible for establishing economic balance through the allocation of industrial resources and encouraging resource utilization in general. These factors contribute to making SMES essential in every nation where they operate. However, despite significant efforts from all stakeholders to enhance their production, SMES till fall short of the standards expected of them. One of the main reasons for the reduction in their anticipated levels of competitiveness is attributed to a poor attitude toward innovation.

Ekon and Isayas (2022) estimate that small and medium-sized businesses (SMES) in Nigeria generated around 48% of the country's GDP during the previous five years (2017-2021). They make up about 90% of the manufacturing sector's firms and over 50% of all industrial employment, with a total population of around 17.4 million (PWC, 2020). Despite the substantial contribution of SMES to the Nigerian economy, obstacles to the sector's expansion and development continue to exist (Amah, 2022). Due to several problems that may be inherent in the operators or result from their external environments, such as frequent and unpredictable changes in public policy, SMES in Nigeria have underperformed expectations (SMES DAN, 2017). In Nigeria, there is also an unsolved problem about the inclusion of a growing young population in the sub-sector, which calls for re-orientation, attitudinal change, and management to accomplish the best possible migration from a jobs-seeking attitude to one of jobs-and-wealth creation. Given the fact that there are more than 190 million individuals in the world, with 65 percent of them being under 35, there is a huge

demand for young people to become involved in entrepreneurship (Olaore et al., 2020). However, Nigerian SMES have not been performing as expected and have fallen short of expectations in terms of their contribution to the nation's economic development (Onugu & Uzundu, 2015). Despite the fact that the SMES sector has significantly aided in the growth and development of the country, its contributions have lagged behind those of other nations.

Numerous studies in various fields has shown how innovation often results in increased competitiveness (Amarakoon et al., 2018; Aziz & Samad, 2016; Naranjo-Valencia et al., 2016; Nishitani & Itoh, 2016; Salunke et al., 2019). However, owing to issues that limit these SMES 'ability to innovate, there is still a significant difference between Nigeria's small and medium-sized businesses regarding how innovation increases competitiveness (Olaore et al., 2020). SMES in Nigeria face numerous challenges that hinder their growth potential. A lack of competitiveness, a negative attitude towards innovation, and limited knowledge of the players that influence innovation all contribute to the struggle (Oladele et al., 2019). This has resulted in lower-than-expected profitability, reduced market share, and difficulty controlling costs (Anoke et al., 2022; Ojide et al., 2022). The unfavourable state of the economy has further compounded the issues, making it even more challenging for SMES to succeed (Idris et al., 2022). Despite these obstacles, SMEs in Nigeria can overcome these challenges by focusing on improving their competitiveness, fostering a culture of innovation, and actively seeking out partnerships and collaborations with key players in the industry (Odusote & Akpa, 2022). By doing so, SMES can position themselves for sustainable growth and success in the Nigerian market. Therefore, the emphasis of this research was on how innovation affects small and medium-sized businesses' ability to compete in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Review of the literature

Innovation

Innovation is the organisation's road to success in the corporate world and a need for preserving it in a market with intense competition (Maier et al., 2018). The primary source of competitive advantage in a contemporary corporate climate is innovation. Although taking chances to be creative is a dangerous move, successful businesses must do so to achieve and maintain high competitiveness (Karabulut, 2015). Proactive businesses take advantage of market possibilities and introduce new products, giving them a competitive edge that helps them maintain their market leadership. Innovation involves developing new goods, manufacturing procedures, supplies, markets, and operational strategies for enterprises (Osuga, 2016). In this research, product innovation, process innovation, and marketing innovation are used to quantify innovation.

Product innovation, according to Karabulut (2015), is the creation of new goods, modifications to the designs of existing products, or the use of novel materials or components in the production of existing products. In other words, even if the change is small or comparable items are already accessible elsewhere, anything that is unique to the company and its product line is considered innovation. Process innovation is the introduction of a new and improved way of production or service delivery by a company that involves major modifications in methods, equipment, tool, and machine (Expósito & Sanchis-Llopis, 2019; Obeng & Boachie, 2018). The success of innovation is heavily dependent on and increased by its marketing of it (Drucker, 2015). All innovation management initiatives that support the commercial success of novel goods and services fall under the category of marketing innovation. It is the effective marketing of a new item or service to meet consumer demands. It predicts requirements for the future and aids in the discovery of fresh market prospects.

Competitiveness

The capacity of a company to fulfil both the needs of its customers and generate a profit over time is essential to the company's ability to compete effectively in the marketplace. This capacity may be accomplished by providing consumers with products and services that are valued more highly than

those provided by rivals in the marketplace. In the words of Cetindamar and Kilitcioglu (2013), competitiveness is a capacity, and its potency must be realized in the firm's daily activities. From the definitions that have been presented so far, it is possible to deduce that the competitiveness of a company is dependent on its flexibility as well as its capacity to make a profit during the course of its existence. An analysis of the existing research demonstrates that the three levels of competitiveness have been conceptualised in a broad range of ways over the years (Yusuf & Albanawi, 2016).

Empirical review on innovation and competitiveness

In research on the influence of strategic innovation on the competitiveness of mobile communications firms in Kenya, Kariuki (2014) discovered that strategic innovation has a cumulative favourable impact on organisational competitiveness. According to the results, businesses that had better marketing, product, process, and service strategies, as well as superior human resource plans, had a greater degree of organisational competitiveness. In Turkey, Gunday et al. (2018) evaluated the impacts of process, marketing, organisation, and product innovation on numerous aspects of a company's competitiveness. They discovered that innovation had a positive influence on these aspects of a company's competitiveness. Yavarzadeh et al. (2015) conducted research in Iran to determine the relationship between organisational innovation and competitiveness. They found that innovation elements, such as organisational innovation, have a positive influence on competitiveness (Rajapathirana & Hui, 2018).

Based on the review, the study hypothesises that:

H01: Innovation dimensions (product, process, and market innovation) have no significant combined effect on the competitiveness of selected small and medium-scale enterprises in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Figure 1: Research model

Theoretical underpinning

The resource-based view (RBV) theory which was proposed by Edith Penrose in 1959 served as the foundation for the research. There are four key criticisms of the RBV. First, it is limited in explaining how organisations can gain a competitive advantage in a rapidly changing business environment (Kleinschmidt et al., 2007). Second, the value creation idea proposed by RBV is static and tautological, making it difficult to test empirically (Kozlenkova et al., 2014; Priem & Butler, 2001). This has also resulted in poor quality research on RBV. Third, RBV is criticised for being static and failing to consider how organisational activities affect resource effectiveness over time (Kozlenkova et al., 2014). However, this criticism has been addressed by later theory refinements. Fourth, RBV tends to ignore exogenous resources, assuming that only endogenous factors are

essential to driving competitive advantage, even though exogenous factors may offer potential as advantageous capabilities (Lewis et al., 2010).

Despite the criticisms above, the theory is found relevant to the study in innovation and competitiveness of SMEs. This is because organisations are comprised of a wide variety of resources and competencies, which are necessary for them to perform their functions and attain a competitive edge. Therefore, the features of an organisation’s resources and capabilities are the primary focus of RBV analysis. The resource-based approach illustrates how organisations may generate above-average returns and competitive advantage by developing, combining, and deploying their resources and skills. Although having resources and capacities is essential, this alone is not sufficient to identify a company’s competitive advantage or organisational heterogeneity. The ability to make logical judgments on which valuable, scarce, and difficult-to-copy resources to utilise and how to use them is essential to gaining a lasting competitive advantage in a given market. In this context, it is important to highlight that other resources are pertinent; nevertheless, due to their failure to adequately explain the consequences of innovation on the competitiveness of enterprises, the resource-based perspective theory was chosen as the appropriate framework to analyse the problem. This is based on the premise that innovation in the organisation, as well as competitiveness, were well explained by the resource-based view in the sense that for businesses to enjoy an improvement in competitiveness or a competitive advantage, they need to make sure that all of the organisation’s resources are put to innovative use.

Methodology

A survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study consist of SMES management staff of the selected SMES in Lagos State. The population comprised 8,396 owners/managers of SMES (SMES DAN, 2021). The sample size was 471 and a stratified random sampling technique was employed. An adapted and validated questionnaire was administered to the respondents and a pilot study was conducted, and the results of the validity and reliability are presented in tables 1 and 2 below.

Table 1: Validity result

S/N	Variables	No. of Items	KMO	Bartlett’s test of sphericity	Sig	AVE
1	Product Innovation	5	0.502	163.267	0.000	0.607
2	Process Innovation	5	0.512	237.206	0.000	0.513
3	Market Innovation	5	0.644	286.274	0.000	0.612
4	Competitiveness	5	0.587	326.731	0.000	0.664

Source: Pilot test (2022)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used as the method for calculating construct validity. The Kaiser-Meyer-Oklin (KMO) measure of sample adequacy and Bartlett’s test of sphericity are the two most important tests that are used to determine whether or not an instrument is valid while doing exploratory factor analysis. In this analysis, the results of the KMO test were found to be greater than 0.5 or 5%, and the result of the Bartlett test of Sphericity was found to be less than 5%, which suggests that the statements that were used to constitute the testing instruments for each variable calculated what was expected to be the case. To further enhance the construct validity of the study instrument, we employed a method called confirmatory factor analysis. The Values of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) higher than 0.5 were used to provide support for the construct validity of all variables included within the study instrument.

Table 2: Reliability result

S/N	Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha	Composite reliability
1	Product Innovation	5	0.729	0.812
2	Process Innovation	5	0.721	0.807
3	Market Innovation	5	0.747	0.791

4	Competitiveness	5	0.759	0.883
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Source: Pilot Test (2022)

To determine whether or not the research instrument could be trusted, the internal consistency approach was combined with the Cronbach’s alpha reliability test. The value of the Cronbach alpha that was calculated is higher than 0.7. In addition, the outcome of the composite reliability is higher than the result of the Cronbach’s Alpha. The standard of 0.70, indicates that the instrument that was utilised for the assessment had a good degree of reliability (Yavarzadeh et al., 2015). To verify the validity of the study’s hypothesis, the collected information was subjected to a multiple linear regression analysis, which was carried out with the assistance of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 computer program. The research model below was evaluated:

$Y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ functional equation

$Y = \alpha_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \mu_i$ equ1 Regression Equations

$COMP = \alpha_0 + \beta_1PI + \beta_2PIN + \beta_3MI + \mu_i$ Equ. (1) Predictive Model

Results and discussion

Data collected were analysed using multiple regression analysis and the result is presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Multiple regression results on the effect of innovation variables on the competitiveness of selected SMES in Lagos State Nigeria

Variables	B	T	Sig	R	R ²	AdjR ²	Std. The error in the Estimate
Constant	41.096	6.392	.000	.379 ^a	.144	.136	19.23337
Product innovation	.222	2.478	.033				
Process innovation	.478	1.053	.023				
Organisational innovation	.843	1.793	.014				
Market innovation	1.028	2.447	.015				
a. Dependent Variable: Competitiveness				F (415, 4) = 17.454			

Source: SPSS Output Result (2022)

Table 3 reveals the result of the multiple linear regression test that was carried out to test the effect of innovation variables on the competitiveness of selected small and medium-scale enterprises in Lagos State, Nigeria. With values showing significance (F (415,4) = 17.454; p-value = 0.000), it depicts that innovation variables have a significant effect on the competitiveness of SMES. The R = 0.379 is the correlation coefficient which represents the strength and direction of the relationship between innovation variables and the competitiveness of selected SMES in Lagos State, Nigeria.

The coefficient reveals that there is a weak positive relationship between innovation variables and competitiveness among selected SMES in Lagos State, Nigeria. Concerning the exact effect of innovation variables on competitiveness, the Adjusted R² = 0.136 shows the extent to which the innovation variables combined to impact the competitiveness of SMES in Lagos State, Nigeria.

The implication here is that innovation (product innovation, process innovation, and market innovation) explains 13.6% of the variations that occur in the competitiveness of selected SMES in Lagos State, Nigeria, while the balance of 86.4% was accounted for by other factors not considered in this study. Based on this result, the fitness of the model is considered good. Furthermore, following the model of the study, the results can be replicated below:

$COMP = 41.09 + 0.222PI + 0.478PIN + 1.028MI + \mu_i$ Equ. (1)

The predictive model shows the multiple regression equation that best predicts the effect of innovation variables (product innovation, process innovation, and market innovation) on the competitiveness of selected SMES in Lagos State, Nigeria.

The model reveals that product innovation with ($\beta = 0.222$; $p = 0.033 < 0.05$), process innovation with ($\beta = 0.478$; $p = 0.023 > 0.05$) and market innovation with ($\beta = 1.028$; $p = 0.015 < 0.05$); provided positive and significant effects on the competitiveness of selected SMES in Lagos State at 5% significance level.

Figure 2: Resultant model of the analysis

The results demonstrated that innovation variables predictors jointly exhibited a positive significant effect on competitiveness among SMES in Lagos State, Nigeria. The results further showed that a unit increase in product innovation, process innovation, and market innovation, increased competitiveness among SMES by 0.222, 0.478 and 1.028 respectively. To sum it up, innovation predictors had a statistically significant combined effect on competitiveness in selected SMES in Lagos State, Nigeria investigated at $p = 0.000$ as such confirmed the objective of the study and provided a rejection of the null hypothesis which states that innovation measures have no significant combined effect on the competitiveness of selected SMES in Lagos State, Nigeria.

The hypothesis for this research was tested, and the results showed that the innovation factors had a significant combined influence on the competitiveness of certain small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES) in the state of Lagos, Nigeria. This conclusion has major implications on a variety of levels, including conceptual, empirical, and even theoretical. The concepts of product innovation, process innovation, and market innovation would all have conceptual ramifications for the competitiveness of businesses. In this sense, they would be a meaning or definition that contributes to the achievement of a desirable result inside an organisation. As a consequence, based on the considerable findings that were achieved, this research provides evidence that this conceptual path is correct.

The present study confirms that innovation factors have a significant positive influence on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES). This finding is consistent with previous research conducted in different countries and industries. Yavarzadeh et al. (2015) found that organisational innovation positively affects competitiveness in Iran, while Kariuki (2014) reported that strategic innovation has a cumulative beneficial impact on competitiveness in Kenya. Rubera and Kirca (2012) also noted that market innovation leads to greater sales through lower pricing or bigger margins. Moreover, Lusweti (2012) found that development methodologies are essential for any business to achieve its goals. These findings align with the results of our study, which shows that innovation factors are significant predictors of competitiveness among SMES in Lagos, Nigeria. Overall, the evidence suggests that firms should prioritize innovation as a means of enhancing their competitiveness in the global market.

The empirical findings reported in this study, which indicate that innovation factors have a significant combined influence on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises in

Lagos, Nigeria, are consistent with the postulates of the anchor theory of the resource-based perspective. This lends credence to the resource-based view as a viable theoretical framework for understanding the relationship between innovation and competitiveness. According to this perspective, organisations must effectively utilise their resources and competencies to achieve a functional and advantageous position in the market. The reviewed studies provide valuable insights into the different forms of innovation that can enhance competitiveness, including organisational, strategic, and market innovation, and underscore the importance of developing innovative practices that leverage the organisation's resources. Overall, the resource-based view offers a compelling explanation for how firms can achieve and maintain a competitive advantage in today's rapidly changing business environment.

Conclusion and recommendations

Based on research findings, innovation is a true predictor of competitive advantage for small and medium-scale businesses (SMES) in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study highlights the significant role of product innovation, process innovation, and market innovation in predicting SMES competitiveness. The conclusions of the research support the recommendation that SMES in Nigeria should focus significantly on innovation. Specifically, managers should ensure that the products they offer are of high quality and capable of successfully competing with others in the market, while also capturing the interest of consumers.

To achieve this, SMES need to focus on improving their operational procedures and removing any components that do not contribute to efficiency. Adopting technologies that foster creativity and distinctiveness in operations is essential to guarantee cost-effectiveness and waste reduction. Additionally, SMEs should examine and enhance every marketing channel and route to ensure competitiveness in the market. Following these guidelines will help SMES build the necessary skills and competencies to remain competitive in the business arena.

Suggestions for further studies

The direction of this study and its findings provide the researchers with an opportunity to make suggestions for further studies. The study adopted a survey design out of other possible designs that could have been used, hence the researchers suggest that a similar study be carried out using a different design to eventually corroborate or refute the present findings. Further studies are also encouraged with a focus on the use of a different sector or domain. This will help to provide a different direction for the study of innovation and competitiveness. The researchers further recommend that more innovation variables be studied as the literature provides that there are different measures of innovation.

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